

Under assured irrigation, two crops of rice are grown during the summer (Feb-Jun) and rainy (Jun-Oct) seasons, with a nonrice winter crop grown Nov-Jan.

More than 75% of the country's ricefields are rainfed, dependent on the monsoon. We are trying to identify high-yielding rice varieties suitable for transplanted rainfed lowland conditions.

IR46 and IR10781-143-2-3 have shown consistently better performance over recommended check Bindeshori and popular improved variety Masuli (Mahsuri) in trials for the last 5 yr (Table 1). Yields have averaged more than 3.0 t/

Table 2. General agronomic characters of IR46 and IR10781-143-2-3 under transplanted rainfed lowland conditions in subtropical Nepal.^a

Variety	Heading (DAS)	Maturity (DAS)	Culm length (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Av yield (t/ha)
IR46	108	135	96	229	3.4
IR10781-143-2-3	105	137	92	233	3.5
Masuli (most popular)	119	150	100	231	3.0

^aDAS = days after seeding.

ha under rainfed lowland conditions (the national average rice yield is 2.2 t/ha).

Both entries mature at least 10 d earlier than Masuli in the normal (Jun-Oct) planting season (Table 2), giving enough time for farmers to plant winter

crops such as wheat, winter maize, or winter legumes. They are resistant to major diseases bacterial blight and blast. They are being distributed to farmers through the rice minikit program. ■

Seed technology

Using electrical conductivity to determine maturity stage for quality rice seeds

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We studied the influence of maturity stage on the keeping quality of seeds. IR50 grown during 1985 wet season was harvested at 27, 34, and 41 d after 50% anthesis. Seeds were dried to 8% moisture content, treated with captan (N-trichloro methyl thio)-Cyclohex-4-ene-1,2-dicarboximide), and stored in cotton and paper-aluminum foil-polythene laminated (P-AF-P) containers for 9 mo.

Electrical conductivity of the seed leachate was measured at 3-mo intervals using Elico CM-82 Conductivity bridge.

Leachate was prepared using 50 randomly selected seeds, soaked in 50 ml of deionized water for 24 h at room temperature, with two replications.

Harvesting 27 d after 50% anthesis gave the lowest electrical conductivity and highest germination (see table). Harvesting 41 d after 50% flowering gave the highest electrical conductivity and lowest germination. Seeds stored in cotton cloth bags deteriorated more than those stored in P-

AF-P bags, and had higher electrical conductivity. The interaction was significant.

The increased electrical conductivity of seeds harvested 41 d after 50% anthesis in storage showed that they are less vigorous and deteriorate faster than seeds harvested 27 d after 50% anthesis. ■

Electrical conductivity of IR50 seeds stored for 9 months. National Pulses Research Centre, Vamban, India, 1985 wet season.

Harvest date (d after 50% anthesis)		Electrical conductivity ^a (dS/m)								Mean	Germination (%)
		At harvest		3 mo after harvest		6 mo after harvest		9 mo after harvest			
		C1	C2	C1	C2	C1	C2	C1	C2		
27	Untreated	36.85	36.83	37.61	37.12	39.62	37.18	40.20	37.25	37.83	93
	Treated	36.83	36.83	37.26	37.10	39.80	37.16	40.18	37.20	37.80	96
34	Untreated	39.41	39.41	40.68	39.86	41.86	40.75	44.86	41.86	41.08	92
	Treated	39.41	39.41	41.61	39.68	42.12	39.86	43.86	40.28	40.78	95
41	Untreated	48.64	48.64	53.63	49.24	55.32	51.24	61.23	51.83	52.47	89
	Treated	48.64	48.64	50.24	49.07	54.83	50.61	60.20	51.61	51.73	90
Mean		41.63	41.63	43.51	42.01	45.59	42.80	48.42	43.34		
Germination(%)		94	94	91	94	90	90	89	94		
LSD (0.01)		0.63	0.59	0.39	0.39	0.55	0.39	0.38	0.45	0.45	0.32

^aC1 = cotton bags, C2 = P-AF-P containers.

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield data and yield component data from routine germplasm screening trials. Publication is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., multiple or unique resistances and tolerances, broad adaptability), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.

Mid-storage correction to prolong viability of rice seeds

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We stored seeds of rice cultivars ADT36, Bhavani, and CO 40 at 8.5% moisture content in cloth bags under ambient

conditions. After 8 mo, half the seeds were soaked in double their volume of a dilute sodium dihydrogen phosphate solution (10⁻⁴M) for 6 h, sun-dried to 8.5%, and re-stored for 24 mo.

Hydrated seeds maintained high germination and vigor (in terms of root length) (see table). Nonhydrated seeds lost vigor and viability. Medium-duration cultivar Bhavani had lower storage potential than CO 40 and ADT36. ■

Germination and vigor of hydrated rice seeds after 3 periods of storage. Tamil Nadu, India.

Cultivar duration	Parameter	Initial	After storage						Biological loss (%)			
			8 mo		12 mo		32 mo		Control	Hydrated		
			Control	Hydrated	Control	Hydrated	Control	Hydrated				
Short	Germination (%)	86	82	90	<i>ADT31</i>		73	89	45	85	47.7	1.2
	Root length (cm)	19.5	17.6	22.1	15.0	20.0	9.2	17.8	52.8	8.7		
Medium	Germination (%)	90	84	95	<i>Bhavani</i>		75	86	16	85	82.2	5.6
	Root length (cm)	18.2	16.0	17.6	15.0	19.5	10.4	18.2	42.8	–		
Long	Germination (%)	89	86	94	<i>CO40</i>		78	88	27	87	69.7	2.2
	Root length (cm)	20.7	18.9	21.1	17.7	20.2	11.5	19.0	44.4	8.2		

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soil microbiology

Influence of wild plant and crop residues on rice yield

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Plant residues and farmyard manure are added to soils to improve their organic matter content and productivity. This traditional agricultural practice has primarily been used to increase soil humus content, water-holding capacity, water infiltration rate, aeration, and porosity; to ameliorate soil temperature; and to supply some essential plant nutrients.

In a pot study, we evaluated the effect of incorporating residues of mesquite (*Prosopis glandulosa*), withania (*Withania somnifera*), and country mallow (*Abutilon indicum*) with rice (*Oryza sativa*) husks and wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) and rice straw, neem (*Azadirachta indicum*) leaves, and farmyard manure on straw and grain yields of rice. Soil had pH 7.6, 0.95%

organic C, 0.073% N, 9.7% CaCO₃, 0.15% TSS. Each pot held 8 kg soil.

For the wild plants, treatments were 3 g residue/kg soil (about 6 t/ha) plus 25 mg N/kg (about 50 kg N/ha). For the crop residues, treatments were 3 g residue/kg soil plus 50 mg P/kg soil. Each pot also received 25 mg P/kg soil. Rice cultivar Shadab was transplanted at 4 seedlings/pot. Pots were arranged in a randomized block design with four replications. N application was lower for the wild plants because their very high antibiotic activities tended to inhibit nitrification.

Effect of incorporating plant residues on rice straw and grain yields.^a

Treatment ^b (g/pot)	Straw yield	Grain yield (g/pot)
Control (no residue)	17.45 c	11.70 b
Mesquite	28.80 a	24.97 a
Withania	23.92 b	19.62 a
Country mallow	24.62 b	22.00 a
Rice husk	16.05 c	11.62 b
Wheat straw	16.92 c	10.75 b
Rice straw	18.05 c	12.10 b
Neem leaf	25.22 b	20.67 a
Farmyard manure	17.92 c	10.22 b

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different (DMRT p<0.5). ^b Plant residue and farmyard manure were applied at 3 g/kg soil.

Straw and grain yield increased significantly with incorporation of mesquite, withania, and country mallow residues, and of neem leaf (see table). ■

Effect of seeding rate on dry matter production and nitrogen accumulation of *Sesbania rostrata*

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Increased crop seeding rates result in increased plant competition for nutrients and light. We evaluated the effect of different seeding rates on dry matter production and N accumulation in *Sesbania rostrata*, a stem-nodulating legume and potential green manure crop for lowland rice.

The field experiment was conducted in 1987 wet season. Soil was a Maahas clay (Tropaquept) with pH 6.3; 11 g organic C/kg; 1.2 g total N/kg; and cation exchange capacity, 34 cmol/kg. P (20 kg/ha) as single superphosphate was broadcast and incorporated before seeding. Seeding rates were 20, 30, 40, and 50 kg sesbania seeds/ha, laid out in a factorial randomized complete block design with four replications. Plot size was 20 m².

Sesbania seeds pretreated for 30 min with concentrated sulfuric acid were broadcast into well-leveled, water-saturated soil. The field was kept saturated to 7 d after seeding, then flooded to 0.05 m.

Sesbania was harvested 45 d after seeding. Plant fresh and dry weights were measured and plant density determined from a 7-m² area. A subsample (4 × 1 m per plot) was taken to determine leaf and stem dry matter separately and to analyze N concentrations in leaf and stem. Total N accumulation was calculated.

N concentrations in leaf and stem did not differ significantly with seeding rate (see table). Seeding at 40 kg/ha gave the highest total N accumulation per plant (114 kg N/ha), and highest fresh and dry matter production. Seeding at 50 kg/ha gave lower fresh and dry matter production and N accumulation than seeding at 40 kg/ha.